

Angelo Leogrando^{1*}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^oLUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Primary Energy Consumption in Europe

Between 2000 and 2021 it decreased on average by 1.03%

The Eurostat calculates the value of primary energy consumption in Europe. The consumption of primary energy covers the consumption of energy by end users such as industry, transport, families, services, and agriculture, in addition to the energy consumption of the energy sector itself for the production and transformation of energy, losses that occur during the transformation of energy (for example the production efficiency of electricity from fuel fuel) and transmission and distribution energy losses). The indicator is measured in millions of tons of equivalent oil.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the primary consumption of energy in 2021. Germany is in the first place for the value of the primary energy consumption with an amount of 267 million tons of equivalent oil, followed by France with a value of 224.4, and from Italy with a value of 145.3. In the middle of the standings there are Hungary with a value of 24.9, followed by Greece with an amount of 20.3 and from Portugal an amount of 19.5. Luxembourg closes the ranking with a value of 4.2 units, followed by Cyprus with an amount of 2.3 units and Malta with a value of 0.8 units.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of the primary energy consumption between 2000 and 2021. Poland is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the primary energy consumption between 2000 and 2021 with an amount of 22.50 units equal to a value of 19.10%, followed by Latvia with a value of 18.42% equal to 0.70 units and by Luxembourg with a value of 16.67% equal to a variation of 0.60 units. In the middle of the standings there is Slovenia with a variation of 0.00 units, followed by Finland with a variation of -0.32% equal to -0.10 and Slovakia with a value of -0.61% equal to a amount of -0.10 units. Portugal closes the ranking with a value of -15.22% equal to an amount of -3.50 units, followed by Germany with a value of -15.80% equal to an amount of -50.10 units and Greece With a value of -25.37% equal to an amount of -6.90 units. On average between 2000 and 2021 it decreased by -1.03%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Four clusters are identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: France, Germany;
- Cluster 2: Slovenia, Lithuania, Croatia, Estonia, Latvia, Luxembourg, Cyprus, Malta, Ireland, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Denmark, Portugal, Hungary, Greece;
- Cluster 3: Sweden, Belgium, Czech Republic, Netherlands, Romania, Finland, Austria;
- Cluster 4: Spain, Italy, Poland.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that Cluster 1 is in first place with a value of 245.7, followed by Cluster 4 with an amount of 112.1, by Cluster 3 with an amount of 39.6 and cluster 2

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

with a value of 8.3 units. From a geographical point of view, it is not possible to detect a particular structure as the primary consumption of energy tends to grow above all based on the population rather than the geographical position. In fact, the countries in which the value of the primary energy consumption is more relevant are the most populous countries or Germany, France, Italy, Spain, and Poland.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with Euclidean distance. Specifically, two simplified network structures are identified and a complex network structure.

- Luxembourg has a connection with Latvia for an amount of 0.086 and with Estonia for a value of 0.044;
- Latvia has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.041 units and with Luxembourg for a value of 0.086 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Latvia for an amount of 0.041 units and with Montenegro for an amount of 0.044 units, and with Slovenia for a value of 0.073 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.073 units, with Lithuania for a value of 0.037 units, and with Croatia for a value of 0.0734 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.0734 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.037 units.

There are also the following structures with simplified networks or:

- Denmark has a connection with Bulgaria equal to an amount of 0.057 units;
- Malta has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.072 units.

Conclusions. The primary consumption of energy in European countries has remained quite constant between 2000 and 2021. Specifically, the value of the primary energy consumption has decreased in the period considered of an amount equal to -1.03%. Between 2019 and 2020 there was a significant reduction in the primary energy consumption value. However, between 2020 and 2021 the value grew by bringing back almost to previous levels. The primary consumption of energy did not grow between 2000 and 2021. This value should have grown above all following the convergence of Eastern European countries compared to the countries of West Europe. In fact, the countries that tend to grow in terms of GDP also tend to consume more energy. This condition assumes that the countries of Eastern Europe can still grow in terms of absolute and pro-capita GDP, contributing relevant to the growth of European GDP. The data do not break down the consumption between renewable energy and non-renewable energy. It is therefore not possible to make a comparative analysis of environmental sustainability. However, consistently with the declarations of the European authorities, it is legitimate to expect a growth in the renewable energy component and a reduction in non-renewable energy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6516438>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Individuals with Risk Behaviors in the Consumption of Alcohol in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636364>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est,* <https://ilsudest.it/>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Years of Life Lost for Exposure to PM2.5 in Europe. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799937>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). The Perception of Good Health in Europe. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799948>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Healthy Life Expectancy in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799956>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Nitrate in Groundwater in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799995>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Ammonia Emissions in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806877>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Use of Hazardous Pesticides in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806908>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Areas Cultivated with Organic Agriculture in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806941>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Public Expenditure for Research and Development in Agriculture in EU, USA, and Japan. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806965>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). The Material and Social Deprivation in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811428>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Workers at Risk of Poverty in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811442>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Turnover in the Service Sector in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811492>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). People Who Remain Poor Even After Social Transfers in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811683>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). The Economic Sentiment Indicator in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811634>

Magazzino, C., & Leogrando, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: a panel data approach. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrando, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). People Who Live in Families With Low Work Intensity in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811718>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). The Housing Deprivation Rate in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811736>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Fatal accidents at work in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7817456>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). The Trust of Merchant in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812107>

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrando, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. *A Data-Driven Analysis* (No. 115763). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Laureti, L., Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrando, A. (2023). The Impact of Renewable Electricity Output on Sustainability in the Context of Circular Economy: A Global Perspective. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2160.

Appendix

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Germany</i>	267	15	<i>Portugal</i>	19,5
2	<i>France</i>	224,4	16	<i>Bulgaria</i>	18,6
3	<i>Italy</i>	145,3	17	<i>Slovakia</i>	16,3
4	<i>Spain</i>	112,1	18	<i>Denmark</i>	16,2
5	<i>Poland</i>	104	19	<i>Ireland</i>	13,9
6	<i>Netherlands</i>	60,8	20	<i>Croatia</i>	8,3
7	<i>Belgium</i>	48,8	21	<i>Lithuania</i>	6,6
8	<i>Sweden</i>	43,8	22	<i>Slovenia</i>	6,3
9	<i>Czechia</i>	39,6	23	<i>Estonia</i>	4,5
10	<i>Romania</i>	33,1	24	<i>Latvia</i>	4,5
11	<i>Austria</i>	31,6	25	<i>Luxembourg</i>	4,2
12	<i>Finland</i>	31,5	26	<i>Cyprus</i>	2,3
13	<i>Hungary</i>	24,9	27	<i>Malta</i>	0,8
14	<i>Greece</i>	20,3			

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Poland	19,10	22,50	15	Slovakia	-0,10	-0,61
2	Latvia	0,70	18,42	16	Spain	-2,40	-2,10
3	Luxembourg	0,60	16,67	17	Estonia	-0,10	-2,17
4	Austria	4,10	14,91	18	Sweden	-2,20	-4,78
5	Croatia	0,50	6,41	19	Romania	-1,80	-5,16
6	Hungary	1,30	5,51	20	France	-14,60	-6,11
7	Bulgaria	0,90	5,08	21	Belgium	-3,60	-6,87
8	Lithuania	0,10	1,54	22	Netherlands	-6,10	-9,12
9	Ireland	0,20	1,46	23	Italy	-20,80	-12,52
10	Czechia	0,40	1,02	24	Denmark	-2,90	-15,18
11	Cyprus	0,00	0,00	25	Portugal	-3,50	-15,22
12	Malta	0,00	0,00	26	Germany	-50,10	-15,80
13	Slovenia	0,00	0,00	27	Greece	-6,90	-25,37
14	Finland	-0,10	-0,32				

Country	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010
Belgium	52,4	52,1	50,1	52,6	52,4	51,6	51,5	50,4	51,2	50,1	53,4
Bulgaria	17,7	18,4	18,4	18,7	18,2	19,2	19,9	19,5	19	16,9	17,4
Czechia	39,2	40,2	40,7	42,5	43,1	42,5	43,5	43,7	42,5	40,2	42,5
Denmark	19,1	19,7	19,4	20,5	20	19,4	20,8	20,4	19,9	19,1	19,9
Germany	317,1	327,1	319,4	321,9	323,7	321,6	332,8	315,8	320,8	299,9	315,2
Estonia	4,6	4,8	4,5	4,9	5,2	5,3	5,2	6,2	5,4	4,3	5,8
Ireland	13,7	14,6	14,9	14,5	14,8	15	15,1	16	15,7	14,9	14,7
Greece	27,2	28,1	28,5	29,2	29,7	30,3	30,3	30,3	30,5	29,4	27,2
Spain	114,5	117,5	121,3	126,1	132,8	136	136,2	138,8	133,9	123	123
France	239	247,3	248,8	254,9	259,2	260,9	256,1	252,7	255,5	246,4	254,5
Croatia	7,8	8,2	8,5	9	8,9	9,1	9,1	9,4	9,2	9	8,9
Italy	166,1	165,4	166,7	175,8	177,7	180,8	179	178,7	176,1	164,1	167,3
Cyprus	2,3	2,4	2,4	2,6	2,4	2,5	2,6	2,7	2,9	2,8	2,7
Latvia	3,8	4,1	4	4,3	4,4	4,5	4,7	4,8	4,6	4,4	4,6
Lithuania	6,5	7,5	8,1	8,4	8,6	8,1	7,9	8,1	8,3	7,8	6,2
Luxembourg	3,6	3,8	4	4,2	4,7	4,8	4,7	4,6	4,6	4,3	4,6
Hungary	23,6	24,4	24,2	25	24,9	26,3	26	25,4	25,2	24	24,6
Malta	0,8	0,9	0,8	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9	1	1	0,9	0,9
Netherlands	66,9	69	69,1	70,5	71,4	70,1	69,5	69,4	69,9	67,6	71,7
Austria	27,5	29,1	29,3	30,9	31,2	32,7	32,6	32,2	32,5	30,7	32,9
Poland	84,9	86	85,1	87	87	88	92,3	91,9	93,1	89,5	96,6
Portugal	23	23,3	24,4	23,6	24,2	24,9	24	23,9	23,6	23,6	22,7
Romania	34,9	35,2	36,5	38,3	37,3	36,1	37,5	37,4	37,3	32,7	33

Slovenia	6,3	6,7	6,8	6,8	7	7,3	7,2	7,3	7,7	6,8	7
Slovakia	16,4	17,2	17,3	17,3	16,9	17,4	17,2	16,4	17	15,5	16,7
Finland	31,6	32,6	34,2	36,1	36,6	33,6	36,7	36	34,5	32,3	35,4
Sweden	46	48,5	49,1	48,5	50,5	49	47,7	47,4	47,3	43,1	48,3
Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Belgium	49,5	47,1	48,6	45,2	45,7	48,5	48,5	46,5	48,4	43,9	48,8
Bulgaria	18,6	17,8	16,5	17,3	18	17,7	18,3	18,4	18,2	17,2	18,6
Czechia	40,9	40,4	40,7	39	39,4	39,7	40,4	40,5	39,7	37,6	39,6
Denmark	18,5	17,7	17,8	16,9	16,8	17,3	17,4	17,4	16,8	15,4	16,2
Germany	297,8	301,1	308,3	293,6	295,9	297,6	298,1	292	285,2	262,1	267
Estonia	5,7	5,2	5,7	5,5	4,8	6	5,8	5,6	4,7	4,3	4,5
Ireland	13,6	13,7	13,1	13,3	14	14,7	14,4	14,6	14,7	13,5	13,9
Greece	26,7	26,5	23,4	23,3	23,4	23,1	23,2	22,6	22,3	19,2	20,3
Spain	122,7	123	115,7	113,8	118,2	118,4	124,9	124,3	120,6	105	112,1
France	249,1	249	250,4	239,7	244,3	239,9	239,1	238,6	235,1	208	224,4
Croatia	8,7	8,2	8	7,6	8	8,1	8,3	8,2	8,2	7,8	8,3
Italy	162	156,6	152,1	142,7	149,1	148	149	147,2	145,9	132,3	145,3
Cyprus	2,7	2,5	2,2	2,2	2,3	2,4	2,5	2,6	2,5	2,2	2,3
Latvia	4,3	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,3	4,3	4,5	4,7	4,6	4,3	4,5
Lithuania	5,9	6	5,8	5,8	5,8	6	6,2	6,4	6,3	6,2	6,6
Luxembourg	4,5	4,4	4,3	4,2	4,1	4,2	4,3	4,5	4,5	3,9	4,2
Hungary	24,4	23,1	22,4	22	23,3	23,7	24,5	24,5	24,6	23,9	24,9
Malta	0,9	1	0,9	0,9	0,8	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,7	0,8
Netherlands	67,1	66,8	66,2	62,3	64	65,1	65,1	64,4	63,6	58,5	60,8
Austria	32	31,7	32,1	30,8	31,7	32	32,8	31,8	32,3	29,9	31,6
Poland	96,6	92,8	93,4	89,5	90,1	94,8	99,1	104,1	100,2	96,9	104
Portugal	22	21	21	20,7	21,7	21,8	22,8	22,7	22,1	19,5	19,5
Romania	33,5	33,3	30,4	30,1	30,8	30,7	32,5	32,6	32,1	30,9	33,1
Slovenia	7,1	6,8	6,7	6,4	6,3	6,6	6,7	6,7	6,5	6,2	6,3
Slovakia	16	15,6	15,7	14,8	15,2	15,4	16,2	15,8	16	15,2	16,3
Finland	34,2	33	32	32,7	31,2	32,3	32,2	32,8	32,1	29,9	31,5
Sweden	47,6	47,5	46,4	46	43,8	45,4	46,4	47,3	45,8	41,3	43,8